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MUDFLOW AND FLOOD PROTECTION DEVICE

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Abstract

The article describes the design, working principle, and calculation method of a new hydraulic device used to combat mudflows and floods. It has been determined that known devices used against mudflows are placed in the riverbed, and they capture and hold large debris carried by the current in the upper reach. As a result, the riverbed is filled with sediments, and when the next mudflow occurs, there is a threat of the flood. The new device, unlike the well-known devices against mudflows, captures and holds large streams of mudflows in a side chamber. The materials collected in the side chamber of the device (large rock fragments, river stones, gravel, and sand) are extracted from there as building materials, and the accumulated water resources are used for irrigation, drinking, and domestic purposes of the population. The proposed device also allows you to prevent flood events.

Keywords. Mudflow, flood, device, calculation method, flow, inflows.

INTRODUCTION

Mudflows and floods cause billions of dollars in damage to the world economy, causing tragedies and disasters. Almost every year in Azerbaijan, those events cause millions of dollars in damage to the country's economy, including the farms of the population. Suffice it to note that the city of Sheki, one of the oldest cities in the country, was destroyed and wiped off the face of the earth five times as a result of mudflows and floods on the Kishchay River in Azerbaijan. Thousands of people died [1,2,9].

It should be noted that, currently, the fight against mudflows and floods is being carried out separately. In this case, one device is used against mudflows, and other devices are used against floods, which are completely different in terms of structure and operating principle from mudflow protection devices.

Protection dams are usually built on the flood-forming part of the river to prevent floods.

The analyses show that the known devices used to combat mudflows do not give the expected effect, and they collapse prematurely and fail.

All known devices against mudflows consist of solid, impermeable dams of various designs or perforated weirs and floodgates built in the riverbed by controlling its width [1÷10].

All known devices capture and hold mudflow debris (rock fragments, stones, gravel, sand, mud, etc.) in the upper reach of the dam and transfer mudflow waters to the lower reach. In this case, a large amount of silt and solid debris accumulates in front of the dam or perforated weir. As a result, the riverbed is filled with sediments, and the water level in the riverbed rises sharply. This leads to a flood event. At the same time, the flood protection device itself is overwhelmed by sediments and fails prematurely.

A new device for combating mudflows and floods has been developed by us, which differs from the known mudflow protection devices in terms of its constructive solution and operating principle. The proposed device consists of a watershed dam located in the direction of the river in the direction of the flow 1, a side chamber holding debris of mudflows with a slope of the bottom towards the shore 2, a coastal protection wall 3, a partition wall preventing the inflows from falling into the riverbed 4, the side chamber consists of a water intake gateway 5, a watershed wall 6, an inlet-outlet road 7 and a leading channel 8 with a hard grate in front to drain or supply the water to the river (fig.1).

*Fig.1. Mudflow and mudflow protection device:
1-dam, 2-chamber, 3-coastal protection wall, 4-partition
wall, 5-sluiice, 6-watershed wall, 7-road, 8-leading channel*

This is how the device against mudflows and floods is executed.

At the end of the river's catchment area (zone), at the beginning of the river's transit section, depending on the terrain (morphological structure), a side chamber is dug on one of the left or right banks of the river, calculated according to the maximum volume of mudflow discharges, and reinforced concrete walls are built along the perimeter of its contact with the bank. The bottom of the side chamber is sloped towards the bank to facilitate the entry of solid debris carried by the mudflow into the chamber.

To divert mudflow water and solids into the side chamber, to reduce the speed of the flow, and to dissipate its energy, a weir is constructed across the riverbed at an acute angle to the flow axis. One end of the weir is connected to the bank, and the other end is connected to the partition wall. To prevent solids accumulated in the side chamber from entering the riverbed, a partition wall is constructed along the line separating the side chamber and the riverbed. A permeable sluice is placed at the end of the chamber to collect mudflow and floodwater and then take them out and deliver them to the user. A retaining wall is built on the lower bypass to prevent the water flowing from the dam from washing away the riverbed (fig.1).

The working principle of the device is as follows.

The rapidly moving mudflow mass in the river is directed to the side chamber by a watershed dam located opposite to the flow axis. The sediments carried by the mudflow enter the side chamber and settle there. Part of the mudflow overflows the weir and flows into the riverbed and continues its movement. As the flood flow approaches the weir, it suddenly widens and changes its direction by touching the weir. At this time, the speed and kinetic energy of the mudflow are extinguished, and its destructive effect is eliminated. Keeping the mudflow together with solid debris in the side chamber allows us to eliminate the threat of flood in the river. The water-absorbing wall located at the end of the side chamber quenches the kinetic energy of the water overflowing from the spillway and prevents the riverbed from being washed away.

The solid waste (rock fragments, river stones, gravel, sand, etc.) collected in the side chamber is considered high-quality construction material. They are extracted from there and transported to construction sites or factories. The side chamber is used as a kind of sand and gravel quarry.

The device also serves as a reservoir to create additional water resources. Thus, after removing the inactive materials from there, the sluice gates are closed and additional water reserves are collected in the chamber for irrigation or to provide the population with drinking water.

Therefore, the proposed device allows you to solve several problems simultaneously.

METHODS

There is no specific calculation method in the existing literature for designing the proposed device. Therefore, we have developed a methodology for calculating and designing the device. Through this methodology, the design parameters of the device are determined and its resistance is checked.

The device consists of 4 independent elements that work in connection with each other:

1) weir; 2) a side chamber; 3) sluice; and 4) a bottom sill.

The height of the weir, H_{sa} is determined by the following expression, depending on the normal water level in the river h_{riv} and the depth of immersion of the weir in the foundation δ .

$$H_{sa} = \delta + 0,9h_{riv} \quad (1)$$

Usually, in flood-prone mountain rivers, the water depth is usually small, but the width of the channel is large. Therefore, the height of the weir is taken constructively, and on such rivers it is not considered appropriate to take its height more than 4 m.

The width of the weir from the bottom B can be determined by the formula used for gravity-type dams [5]:

$$B = \frac{kH}{f(\gamma_1/\gamma)}, \quad (2)$$

where k is the coefficient of resistance to displacement ($k=1.05-1.5$); H is the pressure in front of the dam, m; f is the coefficient of resistance of the unit to displacement ($f=0,2-0,7$); γ_1 is the volumetric mass of the dam material (concrete) ($\gamma_1=2,4-2,6 \text{ t/m}^3$); γ is the volumetric mass of the mudflow ($\gamma=1,1-2,0 \text{ ton/m}^3$).

The upper width of the weir is determined by the following formula using its slope factor m from its lower reach and the height of the weir H_{sa}

$$b=B - m H_{sa}. \quad (3)$$

The length of the overflow dam, L , is determined by the following formula:

$$l = \frac{S}{\cos \varphi}, \quad (4)$$

where φ is the angle of the dam's location relative to the width of the river.

To mitigate the impact of floodwaters and ensure their free sliding, $\varphi=45-70^\circ$ is adopted.

The dimensions of the side chamber are determined according to its capacity W_k . The capacity of the chamber is determined by the expression Q_{\max} for the maximum mudflow, Q_{\max} , occurring once in 100 years.

$$W_k = (Q_{\max} - Q_{riv}) t, \quad (5)$$

where, Q_{riv} is the average annual flow of the river, m^3/sec ; t is the duration of mudflow.

The duration of the mudflow varies between 2-12 hours.

The length L of the shore side of the holding chamber is found by the following formula based on its capacity.

$$L = \frac{W_k}{RH_k} - \frac{C}{2}, \quad (6)$$

where W_k is the chamber capacity, m^3 ; R is the width of the chamber, m; H is the average depth of the chamber, m; C is the width of the entrance part of the chamber, m.

The length of the side of the chamber adjacent to the riverbed is determined by the formula $L_{ch}=L+C$

The width of the chamber R is taken depending on the terrain. The depth of the chamber H_k is determined by the following formula.

$$H_k = \frac{iR}{2} + H_{sa}, \quad (7)$$

where i is the slope of the chamber across the width ($i=0,02-0,10$); H_{sa} is the height of the dam, in m.

To reduce the speed of the mudflow and ensure its free entry into the chamber, the width of the entrance to the chamber is taken as the length of the spillway C . That is, $C=l$

The height of the coastal protection wall, H_d is determined by the following formula.

$$H_d = iR + H_{ch} + a \quad (8)$$

where H_{ch} is the depth of the channel where the device is located, m; a is the reserve height ($a=0,5-1,0\text{m}$)

The height of the partition wall is assumed to be 0.5 - 1.5 m higher than the height of the H_{ak} watershed dam.

$$H_{ak}=H_{sa}+(0,5 \div 1,5). \quad (9)$$

The calculation of the sluice and the flood wall is carried out using methods explained in detail in the books on hydraulic engineering and hydraulics.

The impact-receiving element of the mudflow and flood protection device is the dam. Its resistance to sliding and opening is checked.

In general, the resistance to displacement of all devices is checked according to the following condition:

$$kP \leq fG, \quad (10)$$

where k is the safety factor depending on the class of the hydraulic device ($k=1,05-1,50$); P is the sum of the forces acting on the device in the horizontal direction kN; G is the sum of vertical (weight) forces holding

the device, kN; f is the coefficient of resistance to displacement of the device on the foundation. If the body of the device is connected to the base by a pin or stud, then $f=0.7$, if the body of the device is located directly on the base, then $f<0.7$ is accepted for different soils [5].

The dam is affected by hydrostatic forces P_{st} in the horizontal direction and hydrodynamic forces P_{din} resulting from the movement of flood masses.

$$P = P_{st} + P_{din}. \quad (11)$$

Since the weir is located obliquely to the flow axis, static and dynamic forces act on it at an angle. In this case, the forces acting on the device are divided into normal P_n , and tangential P_m forces (fig. 2)

Fig. 2. Triangle of forces acting on a dam outlet

According to the triangle of forces (fig. 2) the dam is affected by the forces of

$$P_n = P \cos \varphi, \quad (12)$$

in the normal direction, whereas it is affected by the forces of

$$P_m = P \sin \varphi, \quad (13)$$

in the tangential direction. In the formulas, φ – is the angle of the dam's location in the channel relative to the width of the river.

Hydrostatic force acting perpendicular to the unit length (1 paggonnu meter) of the dam

$$P_{st} = g \gamma_s \frac{H^2}{2} \quad (14)$$

whereas hydrodynamic force

$$P_{din} = g \gamma_s H \frac{v^2}{2g}, \quad (15)$$

is determined with these formulas.

In the formulas, g is the free fall acceleration ($g=9,81$ N/kg); φ is the mudflow density ($\varphi=1,1-2,0$ ton/m³); H is the pressure in front of the dam, m; v is the movement speed of the mudflow, m/sec.

Substituting expression (14) and (15) into equation (11), we get:

$$P = g \gamma_s H \left(\frac{H}{2} + \frac{v^2}{2g} \right). \quad (16)$$

Substituting expression (16) into (11), we obtain the final formula for determining the normal force affecting the displacement or overturning of the dam.

$$P_n = g \gamma_s H \left(\frac{H}{2} + \frac{v^2}{2g} \right) \cos \varphi. \quad (17)$$

The vertical forces G holding the dam in place are determined by the following formula:

$$G_i \sum_{i=1}^n g \gamma_{sa} \omega_i, \quad (18)$$

where γ_{sa} is the volume mass of the material (concrete) of the dam, kg/m³; ω_i is the area of separate figures according to the cross-sectional shape of the dam, m².

The resistance of the device against overturning is checked by the ratio of passive and active force moments determined with respect to the lower edge of its heel (point "0") [12]:

$$K = \frac{\sum M_{pas}}{\sum M_{akt}} > 1,5, \quad (19)$$

where K is the coefficient of resistance to overturning; $\sum M_{pas}$ is the sum of the moments of passive forces; $\sum M_{akt}$ is the sum of the moments of active forces, kN. m

The moments of active forces are determined by the forces acting on the device in the horizontal direction, and the moments of passive forces are determined by the gravity of the device and the hydrostatic forces acting on it in the closed direction.

Since one end of the device against mudflows and floods rests on the bank and the other end on the partition wall, there is no danger of it overturning.

RESULTS

The Balakenchay river, which flows on the southern slope of the Greater Caucasus, is one of the mountain rivers with the most mudflows and floods. The river's cross-sectional parameters at its exit into the transit zone are as follows:

- river width – $S=21$ m;
- depth of the channel – $H_{chan}=4$ m;
- average multi-year consumption – $Q_{riv} = 3.5$ m³/sec

In the period from 1962 to 2022, the strongest mudflow from the Balakenchay River occurred in 1973 [11].

The parameters of the mudflow were as follows:

- consumption of mudflow $Q_{max}=308$ m³/sec
- height of mudflow in the channel – $H_{flood}=6$ m;
- speed of movement of the mudflow – $v=2.5$ m/sec;
- mudflow duration – $t=7200$ sec

Determination of the dimensions of the weir dam. Since the water flow and depth in the river are usually quite small, we assume the depth of immersion of the dam body into the foundation $\delta=0.5$ m and the height of the dam constructively $H_{as}=2.5$ m.

Assuming the pressure in front of the weir dam $H=2$ m ($H_{as}-2.5-0.5=2$ m), the coefficient of resistance to displacement $k=1.3$, the resistance coefficient $f=0.7$, the volume mass of concrete $\gamma_i=2.4$ tons/m³ and the density of the flood flow $\gamma_f=1.4$ tons/m³, we find the width of the dam from the bottom using formula (2):

$$B = \frac{1,3 \cdot 2,0}{0,7 \cdot (2,4/1,4)} = 2,2 \text{ m}.$$

We assume the slope coefficient of the downstream side of the weir as $m=1/2$ and determine its upper width using formula (3):

$$b = 2,2 - 0,5 \cdot 2,5 = 0,95 \text{ m}.$$

Assuming the angle of the weir against the flow ($\varphi=60^\circ$), we find its length using formula (4):

$$l = \frac{21}{\cos 60^\circ} = 42 \text{ m}.$$

Determination of dimensions of the side chamber. The consumption of the water

flow is $Q_{max}=308$ m³/sec, the duration of the mudflow is $t=7200$ sec, the average annual consumption of the river is $3,5$ m³/sec. Based on these values, we determine the capacity of the side chamber by formula (5):

$$W_k = (308 - 3,5) 7200 = 2192500 \text{ m}^3.$$

We assume the width of the side chamber to be $R = 200$ m, the bottom slope to be $i = 0.05$, and determine its average depth using expression (7):

$$H_k = (0.05 * 200) / 2 + 2.5 = 7.5 \text{ m}$$

Assuming the width of the entrance to the chamber to be equal to the length of the dam, i.e., $C=1=42$ m, we find its length on the shore side using formula (6)

$$L = \frac{2192 \cdot 10^6}{200 \cdot 7,5} - \frac{42}{2} = 1440 \text{ m}.$$

The length of the side of the chamber adjacent to the river is $L_{ch} = 1440+42=1482$ m. We determine the height of the coastal wall by the expression (8)

$$H_d = 0,05 \cdot 200 + 4 + 0,5 = 14,5 \text{ m}.$$

We find the height of the partition wall (9) by the formula:

$$H_{ak} = 2,5 + 0,5 = 3 \text{ m}.$$

Checking the resistance of a dam. Using formula (17), we determine the normal force acting on the dam in the horizontal direction:

$$P_n = 9,81 \cdot 1,4 \cdot 2 \left(\frac{2}{2} + \frac{2,5^2}{2 \cdot 9,81} \right) \cos 60^\circ = 18 \text{ kN}.$$

We assume the weir to be trapezoidal in shape and find its vertical gravity force using expression (18):

$$G = 9,81 \cdot 2,4 \frac{2,2 + 0,95}{2} 2,5 = 92,7 \text{ kN}$$

We take the reserve coefficient $k=1,3$ and the resistance coefficient $f=0,7$ and check the displacement resistance of the dam according to condition (10):

$$kp = 1,3 \cdot 18 = 23 < fG = 0,7 \cdot 92,7 = 65.$$

The inspection shows that the break water dam is quite resistant to the hydrostatic and hydrodynamic forces of the flood flow.

CONCLUSION

1. Mudflows and floods cause billions of dollars in damage to the world economy every year. Various hydraulic devices and other measures are used to combat these natural and anthropogenic impacts. However, practice shows that the known devices and measures do not adequately prevent mudflows and floods.

2. Currently, known devices used to combat mudflows and floods capture and hold river debris on the upper reach of the riverbed, and as a result, create the hazard of flood by blocking the river.

3. A new device has been developed that can prevent mudflows and floods at the same time, which differs from known flood control devices in terms of both its constructive solution, operating principle, and functional capabilities. The proposed device also allows for the collection of natural building materials and additional water resources.

4. A calculation method has been developed to design the proposed mudflow and flood protection device.

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